

OPPORTUNITIES OF TUTORING IN A HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

Karimova Nozik Jurayevna

Alfraganus University, Faculty of Pedagogy and
Psychology, 2nd year graduate student
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Annotation: This article describes the methods of solving existing problems in the work of tutors with students, as well as the regulation of tutoring. Also, the possibilities of tutoring in higher education institutions are revealed.

Key words: education, student, tutor, national, society, student, value, institution, spiritual-educational, moral-education, innovation, research, management.

Introduction.

A student of every higher education institution is like his child. Just as parents are always worried about their children, educational institutions today also feel responsible for students' learning and the correct determination of their future activities. In addition to teaching a student, what he does in his spare time, what kind of environment he lives in, his extracurricular interests - everything is important for a higher educational institution.

So, what did the higher education institution do in the past in this process? It is known that, until recent years, work was carried out on the basis of the coaching system in HEIs. In this case, the mentoring system is attached to academic groups as a mandatory burden whether the professor wants it or not. In addition to this coercive burden, as a teacher, there was also a great responsibility. If there are three lessons in one day, the teacher is not too far away from knocking on the door to the assigned groups only during the break or asking the group leader "what's the problem" to know who is there and who is not.

In addition, in this coaching system, although a bonus of up to 25% of the monthly salary is set, in rare cases it is paid up to 20%, and in most cases only 5-15% is paid according to the work.¹ Trainers who help students to develop their independent learning activities are working in educational institutions. However, now they are not group coaches, but tutors. Naturally, their tasks are also different from the previous ones.

Effective education of students, acquisition of spiritual and moral qualities directly depends on the tutor's management of educational processes. Because the Tutor teaches the new teacher of new Uzbekistan to love pedagogical activity, to improve teaching skills not every day, but every hour, to work diligently on oneself, to strive for education to meet the requirements of the times, hard work, truthfulness, expressive and emotional speech, pedagogic tact, creativity, organization, patience, tolerance, perseverance, discipline, such as extremely necessary manners, behavior, in a word in other words, to change one's worldview, to develop tasks and skills, to form the skills to feel the changes happening in the world more than anyone else, and to realize one's own ability to harmonize with the requirements of the time. It is important that the idea and pride of "who we are, the descendants of great people"

¹ U. Mahkamov, D. Mahkamov, N. Mahkamova, D. Ismoilova Organization of tutor pedagogical activities. Tashkent - 2022. "Zebo Print" pages 79-80-83-97.

always echoes in their hearts, not only increases their knowledge, but also develops the concepts of consciousness, thinking, culture, responsibility, attitude development in them. To do this, the tutor should implement new methods in the implementation of educational work, self-sacrifice in students, continuous work on themselves, love for the profession, help with the issues they face in their daily life, at every step, constant sharpening of their minds, self-recognition, building trust, feelings, healthy self-evaluation, changing and renewing one's external activities are important. When students understand the value of a tutor, they develop the qualities of mastering the thoughts of their teachers, being satisfied with their love, and dreaming of working in their profession in the future. In realizing these dreams, it will be difficult for the tutor to develop the student's interest in his profession. Usually, when entering the teaching profession, different knowledge begins to affect students.

As a result of not knowing how to get out of the depressions encountered in student activities, there are cases of disappointment in one's profession. In order to eliminate these situations, tutor students should give importance to themselves, be fully prepared for their profession, always control their attitude towards themselves, depressions and disappointments that occur in teaching activities, to develop the ability to overcome defeats and problems, to follow a healthy lifestyle, to teach high self-esteem, to change the mind, to focus on positive, encouraging, joyful thoughts about oneself, etc. In these cases, it is important to prepare them to learn to accept all their dreams and imaginations, whether they are right or wrong.

In organizing and managing his activities, the tutor should pay attention to the culture of creative thinking of students, analyze their views on what is right and wrong, or the negative relationships that arise, and the complex situation, and attach importance to these situations. shows its effectiveness in improving moral culture. In this process, the tutor should have the ability to think, to see the students in their views, to have the skills to create new positive thoughts between him and them and to strengthen them with confidence, to show his glory. it is important to embody the competences of being able to prove. In order to eliminate narrow thinking in students, it is important for the tutor to explain to students how to get rid of negative and harmful thinking based on the development, updating and application of new knowledge in order to create new creative ideas and expel old ones.²

The tutor is the main leader in the improvement of students' intellectual potential, modern knowledge and skills, socio-economic and other spheres, protection of their interests, finding solutions to theoretical and practical aspects of current issues in higher education institutions. The tutor carries out responsible tasks in the process of education to positively influence the personality of the student, to realize their dreams and goals, to support their initiatives and to form their minds and thinking as a teacher who leads them on the path to happiness.

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² Bendova L.V. Pedagogical activity of a tutor in the network of open distance professional education: diss. candidate of ped. sciences: 13.00.08.- M.: 2006. -251 p.

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In the social policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, realizing the national identity, creating harmony between the individual and the society through the assimilation of national and universal values is of great importance. In this regard, our country has all the opportunities for researching the unique individual-psychological characteristics of young people, students' abilities, talents, internal capabilities. After a person is born, first of all, his parents want his child to grow and mature. In the future, he will grow up as a well-rounded generation who will benefit from something in this country based on his capabilities.

A tutor is an employee who works in a higher education institution, meets the relevant qualification requirements, has high moral virtues, and guides the students of the group assigned to him in their education, as well as in the meaningful organization of their free time from classes makes them, educate them in the spirit of humanity, justice, hard work, love for the Motherland, involve them in the circles and clubs organized within the framework of five important initiatives, carry out activities aimed at eliminating all issues and problems that arise in the process of education in the established order. The tutor regularly visits the residences of students living in student residences, rented and private apartments, studies the conditions and problems of students there, and takes measures to improve them. In his activity, the tutor observes the current legal documents, the internal procedure and rules of etiquette of the higher education institution, as well as this regulation. This article focuses on the position of tutor.

As the concept of "tutor" enters our everyday educational lexicon, what does it mean? First of all, "tutor" ("tutor") is used in the literal sense of a teacher, trainer, instructor - a guide. A tutor is primarily an expert in a certain field, and his main task is to provide a student with certain knowledge and skills. helps the student to understand himself better, to study and make the right decisions in life, to understand the consequences of his actions, to find his interests in life In a word, the tutor is a connecting force between the student and the educational process Winter should become an interesting and productive process. The tutoring method was introduced in ancient Greece as an aid to the basic education process. Currently, in many countries of the world, special training and diplomas are given for tutoring. For example, in Russia, universities specializing in the field of pedagogy have special tutoring courses for bachelor's and master's degrees. Tutoring centers and associations operate⁴. This ancient method is used in the modern world in various forms (formal and informal, in the classroom or remotely). Tutoring is definitely different from formal education. It is made in a lighter, flexible form. Tutors are holders of high responsibility. After all, the tutor's worldview works regularly with the student who is now being formed. The

³ Bespalova G.M. Tutor support: organizational forms and educational effects - M. : 2007. №7. P.51-58.

⁴ Gershunsky B.S. Philosophy of education of the XXI century (In search of practice-oriented educational concepts). - M. : Perfection, 1998. - 60.

main task of such a specialist is to help another person make studying an effective and interesting process. The tutor will have to work both with the whole group and individually. It is the task of the tutor to influence students on which areas of science to emphasize, choose a future profession, if necessary, aim for another specialty, establish a balance between study and everyday life, and manage time. A good tutor is a mentor to the student and a skilled consultant. He brings out the student's strengths and reserve abilities and teaches him to work on his shortcomings. (S. Usmanov, Head of Information Service).

Thus, in the results of the study of tutors, although their dominance has a positive value, it was observed that they have some negative friendly relations. In conclusion, it is reasonable to recognize that more extreme behavior is leading in these relationships, that is, in tutor-student relationships..

Conclusion:

1. In the cooperation between the tutor and the student, the aspects of communication have a leading place in their perception of each other as the subjects of the relationship. Because today, the levels of communication and closeness of the subjects of higher education institutions embodying the official-conventional range of pedagogues, the group closeness is somewhat scattered compared to the individual facts.
2. Tutor's desire towards students is also at the formal level, and formality leads in the tutor's cooperation with them both individually and in groups. It is recognized as a reality of high importance that the results of the "tutor-student" cooperation move to the form of mutual respect and trust at the official level. Therefore, the harmony of the goals of the activities of both subjects of the tutor and student cooperation creates the principles of mutual sympathy and empathy, mutual respect and support.

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